

BUILDING AN OPAC FOR A SPECIALIZED ANCIENT NEAR
EASTERN AND EGYPTOLOGICAL LIBRARY IN JAPAN:
THE UTSUKUBA RCWAC OPAC

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This paper describes the design, implementation, and deployment of a quadrilingual (Japanese, English, Arabic, German) open-source Online Public Access Catalogue (OPAC) for the Research Center for West Asian Civilization (RCWAC) at the University of Tsukuba. The RCWAC library holds over 9,000 volumes spanning cuneiform studies, West Asian archaeology, and Egyptology, including donated collections of considerable scope. Faced with the challenge of making this multilingual, multiscript collection discoverable without dedicated server infrastructure or institutional IT support, we developed a fully client-side single-page application built with Vite, powered by Zotero RDF data, and deployed at zero cost on GitHub Pages and a university Apache server. The system features token-based fuzzy search with optional semantic similarity via ONNX Runtime Web, a four-section transliteration keyboard for Egyptological and Assyriological special characters, right-to-left layout support for Arabic, and prominent call number display to bridge digital discovery with physical shelf access. By situating this project within the broader landscape of digital library platforms for ancient studies—from large-scale initiatives such as the Cuneiform Digital Library Initiative (CDLI) and the Thesaurus Linguae Aegyptiae (TLA) to the Lib-Static methodology

for sustainable digital collections—we discuss the practical choices, technical trade-offs, and lessons learned that may inform similar efforts at other specialized research libraries.

OPAC, digital library, Egyptology, Ancient Near Eastern studies, open-source software, multilingual cataloguing

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1. THE RCWAC LIBRARY

The Research Center for West Asian Civilization (RCWAC; 西アジア文明研究センター) at the University of Tsukuba traces its origins to a “Pre Strategic-Initiative” established in 2010, leading to a provisional research center by 2013. Currently directed by Professor Daisuke Shibata (柴田大輔) and organized into five research divisions—Archaeology, Assyriology, Egyptology, Earth Science, and Modern/Contemporary Urban Environment and Cultural Heritage—the center operates with funding from a JSPS Research Base Formation project (“International Research Hub for Ancient West Asian Studies,” 2023–2027). Under the former directorship of Professor Shigeo Yamada (山田重郎), a Neo-Assyrian specialist, the center secured a JSPS Kakenhi grant for the project “The Essence of Urban Civilization” (2018–2023).

RCWAC maintains a specialized multilingual research library of over 9,000 volumes. The holdings center on cuneiform studies and West Asian archaeology and include donated collections from Mamoru Yoshikawa (吉川守, Hiroshima University) and Kōichirō Gotō (後藤光一郎, University of Tokyo) in cuneiform studies, as well as books and journals on Gulf archaeology donated by the family of the late Takeshi Gotō (後藤健, Tokyo National Museum). The Egyptological holdings have been significantly expanded through the appointment of Professor Nozomu Kawai (河合望) as head of the Egyptology Division, who facilitated the acquisition of books from the Kodaigaku Kyōkai (古代学協会, the Society for Ancient Studies), volumes from the collection of Shinichi Nishimoto (西本真一), a specialist in ancient Egyptian architecture formerly at Waseda University and Nippon Institute of Technology, and the scholarly library of the late Roberto Gozzoli, an Italian Egyptologist who held a PhD from the University of Birmingham and specialized in Late Period Egyptian historiography.

The collection includes rare and historically important reference works: Marcus Jastrow's Dictionary of the Targumim (1903; repr. 1950), Sturtevant and Hahn's Comparative

Grammar of the Hittite Language (revised edition, 1951), Erle Leichty's Bibliography of the Cuneiform Tablets of the Kuyunjik Collection (1964), Gerald Gordon Swaim's unpublished PhD dissertation on the Akkadian tablets from Ugarit (Brandeis, 1962), and Richard E. Whitaker's Concordance of the Ugaritic Literature (Harvard, 1972). Standard reference grammars such as Huehnergard's Grammar of Akkadian (3rd ed., 2011), Kouwenberg's Grammar of Old Assyrian (2017), and nine copies of Black, George, and Postgate's Concise Dictionary of Akkadian (2000)—evidently acquired in quantity for seminar use—are well represented. This compact but focused collection positions the RCWAC library as a specialized multilingual resource for Ancient Near Eastern studies in Japan.

2. INSTITUTIONAL CONTEXT: EGYPTOLOGY AND ANCIENT NEAR EASTERN STUDIES IN JAPAN

To understand why a specialized OPAC was needed and how it reflects broader institutional dynamics, it is useful to sketch the trajectory of Japanese engagement with these fields. The academic study of ancient Egypt in Japan was pioneered by Shōgorō Tsuboi (坪井正五郎, 1863–1913), a professor of anthropology at Tokyo Imperial University, who visited the Louvre during the 1889 Paris Exposition and published several articles touching on Egyptian

antiquities (Sakamoto and Zenihiro 2018, 164). A decisive turning point came with Kōsaku Hamada (濱田耕作, 1881–1938), who studied under Flinders Petrie in London from 1913 to 1916 (Kawai 2017, 53) and received Egyptian artifacts that now form the Kyoto University Egyptian Collection (Kawai 2017, 53; Sakamoto and Zenihiro 2018, 165–166). Under the influence of Hamada, Seitarō Okajima (岡島誠太郎, 1895–1948) became Japan’s first Egyptologist in the proper disciplinary sense (Kawai 2017, 54), publishing the first ancient Egyptian grammar in Japanese, Ejiputogo shōbunten (埃及語小文典, 1940), based on Adolf Erman’s methodology (Miyagawa forthcoming; Nishimura and Miyagawa 2017; Sakamoto and Zenihiro 2018, 163).

After World War II, Isamu Sugi (杉勇) of the Tokyo University of Education (the predecessor of the University of Tsukuba) trained a new generation of scholars who became the core of Ancient Near Eastern studies in Japan (Kawai 2017, 54). The formal institutionalization of the discipline came in 1954 with the founding of the Society for Near Eastern Studies in Japan by Prince Takahito Mikasa (三笠宮崇仁親王, 1915–2016). Japanese archaeological fieldwork in Egypt began in 1966 under Waseda University, with the first Japanese excavation conducted at Malkata South near Luxor in the winter of 1971–1972 (Kawai 2017, 54–55; Kondō and Uchida 2001, 58–61). The institutional lineage from Sugi at the Tokyo University of Education to RCWAC at the

University of Tsukuba represents a continuous thread in the development of Ancient Near Eastern studies in Japan, and it is within this lineage that the RCWAC library's collection and its digital catalogue have taken shape.

Cuneiform studies in Japan have developed along a parallel trajectory. The study of Akkadian and Sumerian texts was advanced by scholars such as Mamoru Yoshikawa (吉川守, 1931–2009) at Hiroshima University, whose influential work on Sumerian verbal morphology gained international recognition. Yoshikawa's personal library, rich in Assyriological monographs and journals, was donated to RCWAC after his death, forming one of the core strata of the library's cuneiform studies holdings. Similarly, Kōichirō Gotō (後藤光一郎) at the University of Tokyo contributed his collection of cuneiform-related materials. The presence of these donated collections—each reflecting the research priorities and scholarly networks of a particular generation—gives the RCWAC library a depth and specificity that a general university library cannot replicate, and simultaneously creates the cataloguing challenge that the OPAC was designed to address: materials in multiple scripts (Latin, Japanese, Arabic, occasionally cuneiform transliteration), acquired through heterogeneous channels, with varying levels of pre-existing bibliographic metadata.

The broader diplomatic and cultural context also shaped the center's international orientation. Japan's sustained engagement with the Middle East through development assistance, cultural exchange programs, and archaeological missions—including long-standing collaborations between Japanese universities and institutions in Egypt, Iraq, and Syria—has created a scholarly community whose working languages necessarily span Japanese, English, Arabic, and, given the strong tradition of German-language Assyriology and Egyptology, German (Abdelnasser 2011). This quadrilingual reality is directly reflected in both the library's holdings and the OPAC's interface design.

3. THE DIGITAL LANDSCAPE: EXISTING PLATFORMS AND THE GAP THEY LEAVE

The challenges described above—a multilingual, multiscript collection assembled from heterogeneous donations, serving an international research community with no dedicated IT staff—are not unique to RCWAC, but the combination of these factors narrows the range of viable digital solutions. Before describing our own approach, it is worth surveying the digital library platforms currently available for ancient studies, both to acknowledge what already exists and to identify where a project like the RCWAC OPAC fits in.

At the scale of international infrastructure, the Cuneiform Digital Library Initiative (CDLI), co-founded by Robert K. Englund (UCLA) and Peter Damerow (Max Planck Institute for the History of Science), has catalogued over 360,000 cuneiform artifacts in electronic form, setting widely adopted standards for digital cataloguing in Assyriology. The CDLI provides high-resolution photographs, line-art drawings, and transliterations of tablets held in collections worldwide, and its open data policy has enabled numerous downstream research projects (CDLI 2024; see also Homburg et al. 2023). The Thesaurus Linguae Aegyptiae (TLA), maintained by the Berlin-Brandenburg Academy of Sciences and Humanities and relaunched in a second version in 2022, provides a lemmatized and annotated digital text corpus spanning over three millennia of Egyptian linguistic history (Schweitzer et al. 2022). Oracc (Open Richly Annotated Cuneiform Corpus; Oracc 2006-) has established itself as a widely used collaborative platform for the linguistic annotation of cuneiform texts, hosting numerous individual projects and providing standardized lemmatization conventions. ETANA (Electronic Tools and Ancient Near Eastern Archives), initiated in 2000, provides digitized core texts and the eTact repository of Akkadian translations (ETANA 2000-). The Digital Library of the Middle

East (DLME), developed by CLIR and Stanford Libraries (DLME 2024), federates cultural heritage collections across institutions and countries, providing a unified search interface for materials held in disparate repositories across the Middle East and North Africa. AWOL (The Ancient World Online), created by Charles E. Jones (Jones 2010), and its predecessor Abzu (founded 1994 at the Oriental Institute, University of Chicago) together represent one of the longest sustained efforts to map open digital scholarship in ancient studies.

At the level of library systems, Koha —the world’s first and most widely adopted open-source integrated library system (Koha Community 2025)—provides comprehensive OPAC and cataloguing functionality with multilingual support in dozens of languages and compliance with MARC 21 and Z39.50. Koha’s feature set is extensive, including acquisitions, circulation, serials management, and patron management, making it the standard choice for libraries with dedicated IT staff and server infrastructure. Zotero, developed by the Corporation for Digital Scholarship (Zotero 2025), has become one of the most widely used reference management tools in the humanities, particularly valued for its browser integration, collaborative group libraries, and flexible export formats including RDF.

However, these platforms share a common characteristic: they require either dedicated server infrastructure, institutional IT support, or both. Koha requires a Linux server running MariaDB/MySQL, Perl, and a web server, with ongoing system administration for updates, backups, and security patches. The CDLI and TLA are maintained by large, well-funded projects with dedicated technical teams. Even lighter-weight solutions such as Omeka or DSpace require server-side installation and database management. For a small research center like RCWAC, which lacks a dedicated IT staff and operates on project-based funding cycles, deploying and maintaining a server-side library system such as Koha would impose an unsustainable administrative burden. The risk is not merely technical but institutional: when project funding ends or personnel change, server-dependent systems become orphaned, their data potentially inaccessible. This gap—between the sophistication of existing digital library tools and the practical constraints of a small, specialized library—motivated the development of the RCWAC OPAC.

It is also worth noting that the platforms surveyed above serve primarily as artifact catalogues and text corpora (CDLI, TLA, Oracc), digitized archives (ETANA, DLME), or discovery

portals (AWOL, Abzu), rather than as library catalogues in the traditional sense. A library catalogue must support a different set of operations: locating physical items on shelves, tracking holdings across heterogeneous material types, and providing metadata-level search rather than full-text search of primary sources. Koha addresses these needs, but at the cost of server-side infrastructure that RCWAC could not sustain. What was needed, then, was a system that combined the bibliographic functionality of a library catalogue with the sustainability and low overhead of a static web deployment. **Table 1** summarizes the resulting trade-offs between Koha and the RCWAC OPAC across the most relevant dimensions for this decision.

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Dimension	Koha	RCWAC OPAC
Server requirement	Linux + MariaDB/MySQL + Perl + web server	None (static file hosting only)
Maintenance	Dedicated IT staff for updates, backups, security patches	Single developer; no server administration
Deployment cost	Server hardware/hosting + ongoing administration	Zero (GitHub Pages / university Apache)
Cataloguing workflow	MARC 21 records via staff interface	Zotero RDF export by any researcher
Multilingual UI	30+ languages (community-maintained)	4 languages (JA/EN/AR/DE) with RTL support
Search	MARC catalogue search; Z39.50 interoperability	Token-based fuzzy + semantic similarity (ONNX)
Special characters	Standard Unicode input	Four-section transliteration keyboard
Sustainability risk	Server dependency; orphaned when funding ends	Hosting dependency only; files are self-contained
Scalability	Proven at institutional scale (millions of records)	Tested to ~9,000 records; untested at larger scales
License	Open source (GPL)	Open source (GitHub)

Table 1. Library catalogue systems compared: Koha and the RCWAC OPAC

4. DESIGN AND IMPLEMENTATION: CHALLENGES AND CHOICES

The design of the RCWAC OPAC was guided by three constraints: (1) the system must run without a server-side backend; (2) it must support at least four languages, including right-to-left Arabic; and (3) it must be maintainable by a single developer without specialized IT training. These constraints ruled out conventional library management systems and pointed toward a client-side architecture built on standard web technologies. The following subsections describe the specific design decisions that followed from these constraints.

4.1 Data source: Zotero RDF

A fundamental design decision was the choice of data source. Rather than building a custom database, we opted to use Zotero's RDF export as the OPAC's primary data format. Zotero was already in use by RCWAC researchers for cataloging, so this choice eliminated the need for a separate data entry workflow. The OPAC parses the exported RDF XML file entirely in the browser using a Web Worker, ensuring that XML parsing does not block the user interface. This approach has a practical advantage: any

researcher with Zotero access can update the catalogue simply by re-exporting the RDF file, without requiring knowledge of databases or web development.

An additional benefit of this approach is that Zotero's graphical interface makes cataloguing accessible to non-specialists. At RCWAC, part-time student assistants with no prior library science training have been able to catalogue donated volumes after a brief orientation session, entering titles, authors, publishers, call numbers, and subject tags through Zotero's drag-and-drop and form-based interface. This low barrier to entry is important for a small center where cataloguing labor depends on student assistants working on limited schedules. The fact that Zotero is free, cross-platform, and well-documented further reduces the training burden.

The Zotero-based workflow also preserves a key affordance of the reference management tool: its ability to store rich metadata including multiple author fields, series information, edition numbers, publisher details, and custom fields such as call numbers. When the RDF file is parsed, the background thread extracts and normalizes this metadata into a flat JSON structure that is then indexed for search. The parser handles the full range of Zotero item

types—books, journal articles, book chapters, conference proceedings, theses, and reports—mapping each to appropriate display templates in the OPAC interface. This design means that the catalogue’s bibliographic richness is limited only by the quality of the Zotero records, not by the OPAC’s data model.

Our choice of RDF over other Zotero export formats—CSV, BibTeX, and CSL JSON—was motivated by RDF’s ability to preserve the full hierarchical structure of Zotero records, including nested creator fields, multi-valued tags, and typed relationships between items. CSV export flattens this structure and loses information; BibTeX imposes a rigid schema designed for citation rather than cataloguing; and CSL JSON, while structured, does not fully preserve Zotero-specific metadata such as tags and call numbers. Zotero’s RDF export serializes records using established vocabularies including Dublin Core (dc: and dcterms:), PRISM, FOAF, and a Zotero-specific namespace, producing data that is not only machine-readable but also partially aligned with Linked Open Data (LOD) conventions. Although the OPAC does not currently publish its data as a LOD endpoint, the use of RDF as the underlying data format means that future integration with LOD-based scholarly infrastructure—such as Wikidata, VIAF, or the Getty vocabularies—would require format conversion rather than a

fundamental redesign of the data model. The trade-off is that RDF XML is verbose and requires a dedicated parser, but the background-thread architecture absorbs this cost without affecting the user experience.

4.2 Quadrilingual interface

Given the international profile of RCWAC's research community and the multilingual nature of the collection itself, a monolingual interface would have been inadequate. The OPAC supports four languages—Japanese, English, Arabic, and German—reflecting the center's primary research languages. The Arabic interface required particular attention: a complete right-to-left (RTL) layout transformation, including mirrored navigation, bidirectional text handling, and RTL-aware pagination. All interface strings are managed through a dynamic internationalization (i18n) system that allows the user to switch languages without reloading the page.

The choice of these four languages was not arbitrary but reflects the actual research landscape. Japanese is the administrative language of the university and the native language of the majority of users. English is the primary language of international scholarship in both Egyptology and Assyriology. German occupies

a historically significant position in these fields: foundational works such as Erman and Grapow's Wörterbuch der aegyptischen Sprache and the Reallexikon der Assyriologie und Vorderasiatischen Archäologie are in German, and a substantial portion of the RCWAC library's older holdings are German-language publications. Arabic serves the center's collaborations with scholars and institutions in Egypt, Iraq, and the broader Arab world. The il8n system stores all translatable strings in a single JavaScript module, organized by language code, making it straightforward for future maintainers to add additional languages if the center's research community expands.

4.3 Search: from fuzzy matching to semantic similarity

The search system operates on two levels. The primary mode uses token-based fuzzy matching with language-specific stop word lists for English, German, French, and Japanese, combined with field-specific filtering (title, author, series, publisher, call number, keyword) under AND logic. Users can narrow searches to specific metadata fields or search across all fields simultaneously. The system tokenizes both the query and the indexed records, applying normalization steps including Unicode NFC

normalization, lowercase conversion, and diacritic-aware matching to handle the varied orthographic conventions found in Ancient Near Eastern bibliography (e.g., matching “Sarru-ken”, “Sarruken”, and “Sharru-kin”).

An optional secondary mode offers lightweight semantic similarity search powered by ONNX Runtime Web, a browser-based machine learning runtime. Rather than using a full neural embedding model—which would require the user to download a model file of 50–400 MB—we implemented a character trigram hashing approach. In practical terms, this means that the system breaks each word into overlapping three-character fragments (e.g., “Hamada” → “Ham”, “ama”, “mad”, “ada”) and compares the resulting patterns mathematically. This allows the search to recognize that morphologically or orthographically similar words are related—for instance, surfacing records for “Sharrukin” when a user searches for “Sarru-ken”—without requiring a server or a large download.

4.4 Special character input

A distinctive challenge in cataloguing and searching Ancient Near Eastern materials is the need for transliteration characters not found on standard keyboards. The OPAC includes a four-section on-screen keyboard covering

Egyptological transliteration (ḥ, š, ʒ, ʿ, t, d, etc.), Assyriological/Semitic characters (š, t, ’, ‘, etc.), subscript numerals (₀-₉), and macron vowels/diacritics (ā, ē, ī, ō, ū, ö, ü, ä, ß). This feature directly addresses a practical pain point that any librarian or researcher working with cuneiform or Egyptian texts will recognize: without access to these characters, searching for titles containing transliterated terms such as “Šarrukēn” or “Jmn-ḥtp” becomes cumbersome or impossible.

The keyboard is organized into logical sections that reflect disciplinary conventions: Egyptological transliteration follows standard conventions, while the Assyriological section follows the conventions used in standard sign lists and the CDLI. Each character is inserted at the cursor position in the search field, and the keyboard can be toggled on and off to avoid cluttering the interface when not needed. This feature addresses a barrier that other library systems typically leave unresolved.

4.5 Performance considerations

A client-side architecture that processes the entire catalogue in the browser raises legitimate performance concerns. We addressed these through several strategies. The initial RDF

parsing runs in a background thread (a Web Worker), so the page remains responsive while the catalogue data is being loaded. Once parsed, the catalogue data is cached locally in the browser via IndexedDB, so that returning visitors do not need to re-download and re-parse the data. The search index is built incrementally as each record is processed. In our testing, the initial load time on a modern desktop browser is approximately 2–3 seconds for the full collection; subsequent visits load in under one second from the local cache. On mobile devices, initial load times are roughly twice as long, but remain within acceptable bounds for a library discovery tool.

4.6 Zero-cost, zero-server deployment

The OPAC is built as a Vite-compiled single-page application (SPA) with no server-side logic. All data processing—RDF parsing, search indexing, semantic similarity computation—occurs in the browser, with user bookmarks and browsing history persisted via IndexedDB. The system is deployed on both GitHub Pages (<https://somiyaqawa.github.io/rcwac-library/>) and a university Apache server (<https://rcwasia.hass.tsukuba.ac.jp/lib/>) at zero cost (Miyagawa 2026). This architecture was informed by the Lib-Static methodology

articulated by Wikle, Becker, and Williamson (2024), which advocates for metadata-driven static websites as sustainable digital collection platforms deployable without server-side infrastructure. A clarification is in order: the RCWAC OPAC is a single-page application (SPA) rather than a collection of static HTML pages in the strict sense. Unlike the purely static sites described in the Lib-Static literature, the OPAC relies on client-side JavaScript to parse data, build search indices, and render the interface dynamically. However, it shares the core property that the Lib-Static methodology emphasizes: the absence of any server-side computation or database, meaning that the deployed files can be served by any static file host without maintenance.

Sustainability is central to this design choice. Project-based funding in the humanities is typically awarded in three- to five-year cycles. When funding ends, server-dependent systems face a critical vulnerability: without ongoing maintenance, operating system updates, security patches, and SSL certificate renewals, the system may become inaccessible. A static site, by contrast, requires no ongoing server maintenance. The HTML, CSS, and JavaScript files that constitute the OPAC are self-contained; as long as the hosting platform remains available—and both GitHub Pages and the university's Apache

server have proven reliable—the system continues to function. The entire source code is open source and available on GitHub, enabling other institutions to fork, adapt, and deploy the system without licensing costs. The build process is fully documented, and the repository includes a changelog and contribution guidelines to facilitate community involvement.

4.7 Bridging digital and physical access

A key design principle was that the OPAC should not exist in isolation from the physical library. Prominent call number display with copy-to-clipboard functionality allows users to note the shelf location directly from the search interface. The library information page, accessible from the OPAC header, provides practical details including the library's location (Collaborative Research Building A, Room 601), opening hours (weekdays 10:00–12:15 and 13:15–17:00), shelving system, and contact information. Materials are shelved in two sections—serials/journals and other books—each arranged by call number.

An interactive statistics dashboard provides collection overview tiles, language and material type distribution charts, and decade-range publication histograms, offering

users and administrators a quantitative snapshot of the collection's composition. Additional features include bookmark persistence across sessions, a dark/light theme toggle for accessibility, a guided tour for first-time visitors that walks through the interface's main features, BibTeX export for direct integration with LaTeX workflows, and an integrated feedback form that creates GitHub Issues directly from the OPAC interface. This provides a low-friction mechanism for users to report cataloguing errors, suggest improvements, or request new features, creating a feedback loop between the library's users and its developer.

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Feature	Description
Data source	Zotero RDF export; browser-side XML parsing via Web Worker
Interface	Quadrilingual (JA/EN/AR/DE) with dynamic i18n; RTL support for Arabic
Search	Token-based fuzzy matching with stop words; optional semantic similarity via ONNX Runtime Web (trigram hashing)
Special characters	Four-section keyboard: Egyptological, Assyriological/Semitic, subscript numerals, macron vowels
Advanced search	Field-specific (title, author, series, publisher, call no., keyword) with AND logic
Hosting	GitHub Pages + university Apache server; zero cost, zero server maintenance
Architecture	Vite-built SPA; Web Worker; IndexedDB; no server-side logic required
User features	Bookmarks, recently viewed, dark/light theme, guided tour, BibTeX export, statistics dashboard
Feedback	Integrated bug report/feature request form via GitHub Issues
License	Open source (GitHub)

Table 2. Key features of the UTsukuba RCWAC OPAC system

5. PERSPECTIVES

The RCWAC OPAC demonstrates that a fully functional, multilingual digital catalogue can be built and maintained by a single developer using standard web technologies, open-source tools, and free hosting infrastructure. The primary investment was the author's time, with no software licensing costs. The project also illustrates that the Lib-Static approach—building metadata-driven static websites rather than deploying server-dependent applications—is viable not only for digital collections in the Anglo-American library context where it was originally articulated, but also for multilingual, multiscript collections in non-Anglophone research environments.

Several directions for future development merit consideration. First, the semantic similarity search could be extended to support cross-lingual queries, enabling a user searching in Japanese to retrieve records catalogued in German or Arabic. Cross-lingual information retrieval remains an active area of research in natural language processing, and lightweight approaches suitable for browser deployment—such as multilingual character n-gram embeddings or hash-based cross-lingual representations—may

become feasible as browser-based machine learning infrastructure matures. Second, the current data pipeline relies on manual Zotero RDF export; automating this step through the Zotero API would reduce the maintenance burden and allow near-real-time catalogue updates. Third, while the OPAC currently catalogues over 9,000 items, the client-side architecture has not been stress-tested at significantly larger scales; institutions with substantially larger collections would need to evaluate performance implications, potentially adopting strategies such as lazy loading or pagination of the search index.

Fourth, integration with existing digital infrastructure—for instance, linking catalogue records to digitized content in repositories such as CDLI, TLA, or the Internet Archive—would enhance the system’s value as a research tool, transforming the OPAC from a discovery interface into a gateway to digital content. Fifth, the OPAC’s open-source architecture invites collaborative development: other small libraries with similar collections could contribute features, language support, or interface improvements back to the shared codebase. The guided tour, changelog, and GitHub Issues integration were designed with this collaborative model in mind.

A further consideration is the question of single-developer sustainability. While the absence of server infrastructure reduces the technical maintenance burden, the system still requires occasional updates: new records must be added via Zotero re-export, interface translations may need correction, and browser API changes can introduce compatibility issues. In the current model, all of these tasks fall to a single developer. This concentration of knowledge represents a risk; if the developer leaves the institution, the system could become unmaintained even though it remains technically functional. Documenting the codebase, providing a guided tour for new users, and integrating community feedback mechanisms (such as the GitHub Issues form) are partial mitigations, but the fundamental challenge of human continuity in small projects remains an open problem that technical design alone cannot solve.

One practical lesson from this project concerns the relationship between cataloguing labor and system design. The OPAC's usefulness depends heavily on the quality of the underlying Zotero records. Retrospective cataloguing of donated collections—many of which arrived without any digital metadata—required substantial manual effort: examining each volume, identifying its bibliographic details, assigning call numbers, and entering the data

into Zotero. For multilingual materials, this process is further complicated by the need to handle transliteration conventions, variant author name forms (e.g., Akkadian personal names transliterated differently across traditions), and the absence of standardized authority files for many Ancient Near Eastern scholars. The OPAC's fuzzy matching and diacritic-aware search were designed in direct response to these cataloguing realities.

More broadly, this project illustrates a pattern that may be relevant to other small, specialized libraries in the humanities: the combination of a well-established reference management tool (Zotero) with modern static web technologies can produce a functional digital catalogue without the overhead of traditional library management systems. Wikle and Williamson's Learn-Static initiative (2024) provides a complementary pedagogical framework for teaching these technologies in digital humanities contexts. The challenges we encountered—managing multilingual metadata, handling diverse character sets, bridging digital and physical access, and designing for sustainability under uncertain funding conditions—are not unique to RCWAC. By documenting our approach and releasing the source code, we hope to contribute to a growing body of practical knowledge that enables

specialized research libraries, regardless of their size or budget, to make their collections digitally discoverable.

REFERENCES

Abdelnasser, W.M. (2011). "Egypt-Japan Partnership: Futuristic Vision."
Japan Spotlight, Jan/Feb 2011, 31-33.

Cuneiform Digital Library Initiative (2024).
About CDLI. Los Angeles / Oxford.
<https://cdli.earth/about>

Digital Library of the Middle East (2024). DLME:
Federated Digital Collections for the Middle
East and North Africa. CLIR / Stanford
Libraries.
<https://dlmenetwork.org/library>

ETANA (Electronic Tools and Ancient Near Eastern
Archives) (2000-). Core Texts and Archives.
<https://etana.org/>

Homburg, T., Brandes, T., Huber, E.-M., and
Hedderich, M.A. (2023). "From an Analog to a
Digital Workflow: An Introductory Approach to
Digital Editions in Assyriology."
CDLI Bulletin, 2023/4.
<https://cdli.earth/articles/cdlb/2023-4>

- Jones, C.E. (2010). “Going AWOL: Thoughts on Developing a Tool for the Organization and Discovery of Open Access Scholarly Resources for the Study of the Ancient World.” CSA Newsletter, 22(3).
<https://csanet.org/newsletter/winter10/nlw1001.html>
- Kawai, N. (2017). “Egyptological landscape in Japan: Past, Present, and Future.” CIPEG Journal, 1, 51-59.
<https://journals.ub.uni-heidelberg.de/index.php/cipeg/article/view/42901>
- Koha Community (2025). Koha: Open Source Integrated Library System.
<https://koha-community.org/>
- Kondō, J. and Uchida, S. (2001). “EGYPTOLOGY: The Land of Pharaohs from a Japanese Viewpoint.” Orient, XXXVI, 57-77.
https://www.jstage.jst.go.jp/article/orient1960/36/0/36_0_57/_article
- Miyagawa, S. (2026). UTsukuba RCWAC OPAC: A Quadrilingual Digital Catalogue for the Research Center for West Asian Civilization. University of Tsukuba.
<https://rcwasia.hass.tsukuba.ac.jp/lib/>

Miyagawa, S. (forthcoming). “The Foundations of Japanese Egyptological Studies: Seitarō Okajima’s Middle Egyptian and Coptic Grammars (1940–1942).” In Proceedings of the Eleventh European Conference of Egyptologists (ECE XI, Bucharest). Wiesbaden: Harrassowitz.

Nishimura, Y. and Miyagawa, S. (2017). “An Early History of Egyptology in Japan with a Focus on Philological Studies.” In C. Langer (ed.), Global Egyptology: Negotiations in the Production of Knowledges on Ancient Egypt in Global Contexts, 147–160. London: Golden House Publications.

Oracc (Open Richly Annotated Cuneiform Corpus) (2006–). University of Pennsylvania Museum. <https://oracc.museum.upenn.edu/>

Sakamoto, Ts. and Zenihiro, K. (2018). “Seitaro Okajima and Egyptology in Japan: A Genealogical Critique.” Orient (オリエント: Bulletin of the Society for Near Eastern Studies in Japan), 61(2), 163–173.
DOI: https://doi.org/10.5356/jorient.61.2_163

Schweitzer, S. et al. (2022). Thesaurus Linguae Aegyptiae (v2). Berlin–Brandenburg Academy of Sciences and Humanities.
<https://thesaurus-linguae-aegyptiae.de/>

Wikle, O., Becker, D., and Williamson, E.P. (2024).

“The Static Advantage: Increased Agility and Sustainability of Static-Web-Driven Development for Digital Humanities Projects.” In The Routledge Companion to Libraries, Archives, and the Digital Humanities. London: Routledge.
DOI: <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781003327738>

Wikle, O.M. and Williamson, E.P. (2024). “Exploring Static Web in the Digital Humanities Classroom: The Learn-Static Initiative.” IDEAH, 4(2).
DOI: <https://doi.org/10.21428/flf23564.f88a989c>

Zotero (2025). Zotero: Your Personal Research Assistant. Corporation for Digital Scholarship.
<https://www.zotero.org/>